

THE IMPACT OF COMPLEX AGROTECHNICAL MEASURES ON THE GENERAL GROWTH DYNAMICS OF LOCAL AND INTRODUCED COTTON VARIETIES

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ABSTRACT

The effects of sowing and thinning times, plant density, irrigation regime, and fertilizer rates on the general growth dynamics of local and introduced cotton varieties were studied comparatively. The agrotechnical measures applied had varying impacts on both varieties. In the Ganja-182 variety, developmental phases began 10–12 days earlier compared to the Beyaz-Altun variety. Higher growth indicators were observed in variants with 74,000 plants per hectare (using a 90x15x1 sowing scheme), sowing conducted on April 25, thinning on May 15, application of N120P75K50 kg fertilizer rates, and irrigation carried out in a 1-4-0 schedule.

Complex agrotechnical measures had varying effects on the main stem height of both local and introduced cotton varieties. In the Ganja-182 variety, with a plant density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 scheme), sowing on April 25, thinning on May 15, application of N120P75K50 kg fertilizer per hectare, in the variant where the 1-4-0 irrigation schedule was applied, the main stem height reached 114–116 cm, which is 10–14 cm taller than in the other variants. In the Beyaz-Altun variety, the same variant also resulted in a taller main stem, reaching 102–107 cm.

Keywords: agrotechnical measures, cotton, sowing scheme, thinning, fertilization, irrigation regime, growth phases, main stem.

Introduction

Cotton is the most valuable among technical crops. One of the decisive factors in the dynamic development of cotton production is the creation of new intensive-type varieties and their widespread adoption in production. Research indicates that the potential for creating new varieties through effective selection based on the variability of existing commercial varieties has been exhausted. Therefore, breeders are now tasked with developing new theoretically grounded synthetic methods and various genetic-selection approaches aimed at creating a rich gene pool for obtaining new plant varieties. The intensification of breeding work, obtaining initial material for hybridization, improving specific traits of existing varieties, developing methodological approaches for creating new cotton varieties, and addressing and studying many of the existing issues in mutation breeding are among the most pressing and relevant challenges today.

As stated in the “State Program on the Development of Cotton Production in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2017–2022,” the comprehensive development of cotton growing in Azerbaijan dates back to the early 1970s. Currently, the application of innovative technologies in cotton production should aim to increase output not by expanding cultivated areas, but by improving productivity per unit area. This qualitative transformation is underpinned by consistent and systematic measures implemented by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Azerbaijan with the support of the state [1].

In the “Strategic Road Map for the Production and Processing of Agricultural Products in the Republic of Azerbaijan,” approved by Decree No. 1138 of the President of the Republic of

Azerbaijan dated December 6, 2016, the development of environmentally friendly agricultural production has been identified as a key priority.

This Strategic Road Map outlines a vision for the development of the country's agricultural sector up to the year 2020, and a target vision for the period up to 2025. It reflects the existence of a clear and phased implementation plan by the state to achieve both medium- and long-term strategic development goals in the agricultural sector.

Another important direction in the work of creative selection is to pay due attention to the development of ecologically plastic varieties. The varieties developed usually perform well only within a limited ecological zone and are unable to demonstrate their full potential over a wide area. Among the created varieties, those obtained using new methods constitute a minority. Using many valuable traits of forms in the cotton collection as donors is one of the general tasks facing breeders and geneticists.

The effects of different sowing methods, sowing times, thinning periods, fertilizer rates, and irrigation regimes on the seeds of cotton varieties have varied depending on the biological and morphological characteristics of the varieties. This effect has also been observed at different stages of plant development.

Əsgərov M.M. (2019) The preservation of soil fertility plays a crucial role in increasing the productivity of all agricultural crops. Often, mineral fertilizers do not give the same efficiency in all types of soils. The effectiveness of fertilizers depends on the soil type, its fertility, the physical and chemical properties of the fertilizer, the preceding crop, and so on. For example, in chestnut soils, nitrogen has more effect compared to phosphorus, whereas in gray soils, phosphorus has a greater effect compared to nitrogen. Fertilizers have a better effect on soils with poor nutrient content, while their efficiency decreases in well-supplied soils. The use of fertilizers reaches its maximum under normal moisture conditions and minimum under low moisture [2, pp. 49-52].

Cotton is demanding of nutrients throughout all stages of its development. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the timing of fertilizer application.

The gray-steppe soils of the Mil-Karabakh regions are poorly supplied with nutrients. To obtain a high yield of cotton with quality fiber, it is important to apply nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorus fertilizers at optimal rates. Based on the results of more than 20 years of research, applying fertilizers at the rate of N250P200K75 kg per hectare in these regions has consistently produced good results.

N.Y. Seyidaliyev, X.Q. Khalilov, and M.Z. Mammadova (2021) The study notes that as a result of the applied agrotechnical measures, the height of the main stem in the Ganja-110 variety under row sowing with the application of N120 P75 K50 kg per hectare was 113–116 cm, while in the Ganja-103 variety it was 117–125 cm. Under the same agrotechnical conditions, the number of monopodial branches in the Ganja-110 variety was 2.2, and the number of sympodial branches was 18. In the Ganja-103 variety, the number of monopodial branches was 2.1, and the number of sympodial branches was 15. In the variants sown by the conventional sowing method, the indicators for both varieties were considerably lower [6, pp. 4–8].

Ismayilova A.I. (2022) in her research shows that plant density is considered one of the factors affecting the growth, development, and yield level of cotton. It is known that in sparse sowing, plants develop strongly and each individual plant produces a high yield. However, because the number of plants per unit area is low in sparse sowing, the total yield is also low. Conversely, if the number of plants per area is high and their distribution is limited to a certain nutrient area, their height will be relatively low, but the overall yield level will be high. Plants grown at densities higher than the norm have shorter height, are weak, and also produce lower yields [3, pp. 151–152].

Seyidaliyev N.Y. and Khalilov X.Q. (2022), based on their experiments and close acquaintance with the farms of landowners and cotton-growing farmers, identified existing problems and provided recommendations for their resolution. The main problems are as follows: the lack of agrochemical

analysis of soils intended for cotton cultivation, improper selection of planting areas, incorrect implementation of crop rotation in cotton farming, failure to clean fields from cotton residues (plant stalks), and the untimely execution of other planned agrotechnical measures [7, pp. 343–349].

Zeynalova A.I. (2019), in her research comparing local and introduced cotton varieties, concluded that local varieties maintain their genetic potential steadily over many years. However, introduced varieties are distinguished by high yields in the first years. After a certain period, their yield significantly decreases, which indicates incomplete adaptation of these varieties. Among the local varieties, “Ganja-103” and “Ganja-110” were planted, while among the introduced varieties, “Beyaz-Altun,” “Flash,” “Progen,” and “Karlo” were cultivated. As noted, in the initial years, introduced varieties showed high yields, but the technological qualities of the fiber and the weight of 1000 seeds were superior in the local varieties. In subsequent years, all indicators of the local varieties were higher [8, pp. 65–66].

Seydaliyev N.Y., Khalilov X.Q., and Mammadova M.Z. (2022) note that for the Ganja-110 variety, the sowing scheme of 90x10x1 (111,000 plants per hectare) with a fertilizer rate of N100P50K40, harvesting on August 1 and picking on September 25, resulted in a net income of 1851 manats and a profitability level of 211.5%. For the sowing scheme of 90x15x1 (74,000 plants per hectare) with the same fertilizer rate and harvesting dates, the net income and profitability were 1628 manats and 186.0%, respectively. With the sowing scheme of 90x10x1 (111,000 plants per hectare), fertilizer rate of N120P75K50, harvesting on August 12, and picking on October 15, the net income was 1660 manats and profitability 189.7%. In the variant with N120P75K50 fertilizer and harvesting and picking on the same dates, the net income was 1546 manats and profitability 176.6% [5, pp. 343–349].

Materials and Methods

The effects of different sowing schemes, plant density, sowing and thinning times, fertilizer rates, and irrigation regimes on the structural characteristics of the cotton varieties “Ganja-182” and “Beyaz-Altun” were comparatively studied. The research was conducted on the farm of Vagif Ahmadov, located in the Gunelli settlement of Beylagan district. The methods developed by B.A. Dospekhov, N.N. Baranova, and S.Z. Allahyarov were used for setting up the experiment in the research area. The research object was the farm of Vagif Ahmadov in the Gunelli settlement of Beylagan district.

The experiment consisted of 8 variants, each with 4 replications. In the field, the length of each replication was 20 meters, and the width was 2.4 meters. The area of one replication was 48 m², the area of one variant was 192 m², and the total area of the experimental field was 1152 m².

Results and Discussion

The effects of sowing methods, fertilizer rates, flowering, and harvesting times on the formation of true leaves and the onset of general development phases in the plants varied depending on the daily characteristics of the varieties.

In the research conducted in 2024, slight differences observed within the same variety are attributed to the influence of climate and irrigation. The agrotechnical measures applied in the study did not have a uniform effect.

Mammadzada X.Y. (2022) notes that in our country, cotton varieties are cultivated using various innovative technologies. Comparative study of sowing by traditional and ridge (tirə) technologies, as well as the investigation of their effects on yield and fiber quality indicators, is an essential requirement. It is necessary to completely revise the technologies applied in cotton growing, introduce high-yielding and early-maturing varieties, strengthen the material and technical base of cotton farming, develop effective measures against cotton diseases and pests, and thereby increase the productivity of this crop and improve all its structural characteristics. Ridge sowing and optimal fertilizer rates yield high results in all farms [4, pp. 12–13]. Djumayev Ş.V. (2017) states that the main task of selection work is to obtain new high-yielding and early-maturing varieties belonging to medium-staple cotton types. If it is possible to shorten the vegetation period of such cotton varieties

by 20–25 days, the yield per hectare can be increased by 30–40%. There are great opportunities to increase the efficiency of selection through hybridization methods, both in the crossing process and in subsequent work on hybridization materials [9, pp. 38–39].

Khan F.Z., Rehman S.U., Abid M.A., Malik W., Hanif C.M., Bilal M., Farhan U. (2015) state that there are 35 species of cotton worldwide, of which 5 are cultivated commercially. Varieties of upland cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) are grown in many parts of the world, including Azerbaijan. Compared to fine-staple cotton, the vegetation period of upland cotton is somewhat shorter. The sowing material must possess high varietal purity. The varietal purity of sowing material is determined by the proportion of seeds retaining all hereditary traits and characteristics of the sown variety, expressed as a percentage. The higher the varietal purity, the more uniform and free from mixture the plants will be, resulting in higher yields. Consequently, the genetic characteristics of the variety will also be preserved for a longer time [10, pp. 119–126].

The indicators differed in both varieties. As seen from the table, in the Ganja-182 variety, under the sowing scheme of 90x10x1 (111,000 plants), fertilizer norm N100P50K40, sowing on April 15, thinning on May 5, and irrigation according to the 1-3-0 scheme, the first true leaves emerged on May 13, the second on May 20, and the third on May 27. The budding stage occurred on June 13, the flowering stage on July 5, and the maturation stage extended to August 26.

In the variant with a sowing scheme of 74,000 plants (90x15x1), sowing on April 15, the same fertilizer norm (N100P50K40), thinning on May 5, and irrigation according to the 1-3-0 scheme, the first true leaves appeared on May 10, the second on May 19, the third on May 23. The budding stage was observed on June 12, the flowering stage on July 4, and the maturation stage on August 26.

In the variant with a sowing scheme of 111,000 plants (90x10x1), sowing on April 25, thinning on May 15, fertilizer norm N120P75K50, and irrigation according to the 1-4-0 scheme, the first true leaves appeared on May 18, the second on May 26, and the third on May 28. The budding stage occurred on June 17, flowering on July 9, and maturation on September 2.

In the variant with a sowing scheme of 74,000 plants (90x15x1), sowing on April 25, thinning on May 15, fertilizer norm N120P75K50, and irrigation according to the 1-4-0 scheme, the first true leaves appeared on May 16, the second on May 26, and the third on May 31. The budding stage occurred on June 16, the flowering stage on July 12, and the maturation stage was observed on September 5.

In the Beyaz-Altun variety, under the sowing scheme of 90x10x1 (111,000 plants), fertilizer norm N100P50K40, sowing conducted on April 15, thinning performed on May 5, and irrigation applied according to the 1-3-0 scheme, the first true leaves emerged on May 8, the second on May 20, and the third on May 27. The budding stage occurred on June 10, the flowering stage on July 5, and the maturation stage extended to August 26.

In the variant with a sowing scheme of 74,000 plants (90x15x1), sowing was done on April 15, with the same fertilizer norm (N100P50K40), thinning on May 5, and irrigation applied according to the 1-3-0 scheme, the first true leaves appeared on May 13, the second on May 22, and the third on May 27. The budding stage was observed on June 12, the flowering stage on July 4, and the maturation stage on August 28.

In the variant with a sowing scheme of 111,000 plants (90x10x1), sowing was carried out on April 25, thinning on May 15, fertilizer norm N120P75K50 was applied, and irrigation was done according to the 1-4-0 scheme. In this variant, the first true leaves appeared on May 18, the second on May 30, and the third on June 6. The budding stage was recorded on June 16, the flowering stage on July 16, and the maturation stage was observed on September 8.

In the variant with a sowing scheme of 74,000 plants (90x15x1), sowing was conducted on April 25, thinning was carried out on May 15, fertilizer norm N120P75K50 kg was applied, and irrigation was performed according to the 1-4-0 scheme. In this variant, the first true leaves appeared on May 24, the second true leaves on June 3, and the third true leaves on June 10. The budding stage was observed on June 25, the flowering stage on July 20, and the maturation stage on September 10. As can be seen, the agrotechnical measures applied to both varieties had different effects. In the Ganja-182 variety, the developmental stages began 10–12 days earlier compared to the Beyaz-Altun

variety. The highest indicators were observed in the variants of both varieties where a sowing scheme of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1) was applied, sowing was carried out on April 25, thinning on May 15, a fertilizer norm of N120P75K50 kg was used, and irrigation was conducted according to the 1-4-0 scheme.

Table 1. The effect of complex agrotechnical measures on the overall development dynamics of cotton varieties.

Variants						Formation of the 1st true leaves	Formation of the 2nd true leaves	Formation of the 3rd true leaves	Beginning of the budding (blooming)phase	Beginning of the flowering (blooming)phase	Beginning of the maturation phase
Varieties	Sowing scheme and plant density	Sowing periods	Thinning periods	Fertilizer rates (kg/ha)	Fertilizer rates (kg/ha)						
Ganja-182	111 thousand plants (90x10x1)	15 april	05 may	N100P 50K40	1-3-0	13.V	20.V	27.V	13.VI	05.VII	26.V III
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	15 april	05 may	N100P 50K00	1-3-0	10.V	19.V	23.V	12.VI	04.VII	26.V III
	111 thousand plants bitki(90x10x1)	25 april	15 may	N120P 75K50	1-4-0	17.V	25.V	31.V	18.VI	12.VI	02.I X
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	25 april	15 may	N120P 75K50	1-4-0	17.V	26.V	01.V I	17.VI	12.VII	05.I X
Beyaz-Altun	111 thousand plants (90x10x1)	15 april	05 may	N100P 50K40	1-3-0	18.V	30.V	06.V I	16.VI	12.VII	06.I X
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	15 april	05 may	N100P 50K00	1-3-0	18.V	27.V	03.V I	17.VI	16.VII	08.I X
	111 thousand plants (90x10x1)	25 april	15 may	N120P 75K50	1-4-0	25.V	04.06	10.V I	26.VI	19.VII	13.I X
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	25 april	15 may	N120P 75K50	1-4-0	24.V	03.VI	10.V I	25.VI	20.VII	10.I X

The response of cotton varieties to agrotechnical measures varies depending on their morphological and biological characteristics. Each applied agrotechnical measure has a certain impact on the growth dynamics of individual varieties. In other words, the reaction of different varieties to agrotechnical practices is not the same. The effect of agrotechnical measures on the height of the main stem is presented in Table 2.

As seen from the table, in the Ganja-182 cotton variety, under the treatment with a plant density of 111,000 plants per hectare (90x10x1 spacing), sowing on April 15, thinning on May 5, a fertilizer application rate of N100P50K40 kg/ha, and an irrigation schedule of 1-3-0, the height of the main stem

was 37.6 cm at the budding stage, 66.2 cm at the flowering stage, and 103–110 cm at the maturity stage.

In the treatment with a plant density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 spacing), also sown on April 15, thinned on May 5, with the same fertilizer rate of N100P50K40 kg/ha and irrigation schedule of 1-3-0, the main stem height was 38.8 cm at the budding stage, 67.6 cm at the flowering stage, and 108–113 cm at the maturity stage.

Under the treatment with a plant density of 111,000 plants per hectare (90x10x1 spacing), sowing on April 25, thinning on May 15, a fertilizer rate of N120P75K50 kg/ha, and an irrigation schedule of 1-4-0, the main stem height was 37.6 cm at the budding stage, 67.9 cm at the flowering stage, and 107–114 cm at the maturity stage.

In the variant with a plant density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 spacing), sown on April 25, thinned on May 15, with the same fertilizer rate of N120P75K50 kg/ha and irrigation schedule of 1-4-0, the main stem height reached 39.5 cm at the budding stage, 69.2 cm at the flowering stage, and 114–116 cm at the maturity stage.

In the Beyaz-Altun cotton variety, under the treatment with a plant density of 111,000 plants per hectare (90x10x1 spacing), sown on April 15, thinned on May 5, with a fertilizer rate of N100P50K40 kg/ha and an irrigation schedule of 1-3-0, the height of the main stem was 27.1 cm at the budding stage, 60.4 cm at the flowering stage, and 99–102 cm at the maturity stage.

In the treatment with a plant density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 spacing), also sown on April 15, thinned on May 5, with the same fertilizer rate (N100P50K40 kg/ha) and irrigation schedule (1-3-0), the main stem height reached 28.4 cm at the budding stage, 55.7 cm at the flowering stage, and 100–106 cm at the maturity stage.

In the variant with 111,000 plants per hectare (90x10x1 spacing), sown on April 25, thinned on May 15, with a fertilizer application of N120P75K50 kg/ha and an irrigation schedule of 1-4-0, the main stem height was 28.6 cm at the budding stage, 56.6 cm at the flowering stage, and 101–107 cm at the maturity stage.

Finally, in the treatment with a plant density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 spacing), sown on April 25, thinned on May 15, with the same fertilizer and irrigation treatment (N120P75K50 kg/ha, 1-4-0), the main stem height was 30.7 cm at the budding stage, 60.3 cm at the flowering stage, and 102–110 cm at the maturity stage.

The complex agrotechnical measures had varying effects on the main stem height in both local and introduced cotton varieties. In the Ganja-182 variety, under the treatment with a plant density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 spacing), sown on April 25, thinned on May 15, with a fertilizer application rate of N120P75K50 kg/ha and an irrigation schedule of 1-4-0, the height of the main stem reached 114–116 cm, which was 10–14 cm taller compared to the other treatments.

In the Beyaz-Altun variety, the same treatment also resulted in greater stem height, reaching 102–107 cm.

Table 2. The Effect of Complex Agrotechnical Measures on the Main Stem Height of Cotton Varieties.

Variants						Main stem height (cm)		
Varieties	Sowing pattern and plant density	Sowing periods	Thinning periods	Fertilizer rates (kg/ha)	Irrigation regime	Budding	Flowering	Ripening
Ganja-182	111 thousand plants (90x10x1)	15 april	05 may	N ₁₀₀ P ₅₀ K ₄₀	1-3-0	37,6	66,2	103-110
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	15 april	05 may	N ₁₀₀ P ₅₀ K ₄₀	1-3-0	38,8	67,6	108-113

	111 thousand plants bitki(90x10x1)	25 april	15 may	N ₁₂₀ P ₇₅ K ₅₀	1-4-0	37,6	67,9	107-114
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	25 april	15 may	N ₁₂₀ P ₇₅ K ₅₀	1-4-0	39,5	69,2	114-116
Beyaz-Altun	111 thousand plants (90x10x1)	15 april	05 may	N ₁₀₀ P ₅₀ K ₄₀	1-3-0	27,1	60,4	99-102
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	15 april	05 may	N ₁₀₀ P ₅₀ K ₀₀	1-3-0	28,4	55,7	100-106
	111 thousand plants (90x10x1)	25 april	15 may	N ₁₂₀ P ₇₅ K ₅₀	1-4-0	28,6	56,6	101-107
	74 thousand plants (90x15x1)	25 april	15 may	N ₁₂₀ P ₇₅ K ₅₀	1-4-0	30,7	60,3	102-110

Conclusion

1. The applied agrotechnical measures had different effects on both studied cotton varieties. In the Ganja-182 variety, the developmental phases began 10–12 days earlier compared to the Beyaz-Altun variety. The highest performance indicators in both varieties were recorded in the treatment with a seeding density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 spacing), sowing carried out on April 25, thinning on May 15, application of N120P75K50 kg/ha fertilizer, and irrigation according to the 1-4-0 schedule.

2. The complex agrotechnical measures affected the main stem height in both local and introduced cotton varieties in different ways. In the Ganja-182 variety, under the treatment with a plant density of 74,000 plants per hectare (90x15x1 spacing), sowing on April 25, thinning on May 15, application of N120P75K50 kg/ha fertilizer, and an irrigation schedule of 1-4-0, the main stem height reached 114–116 cm, which was 10–14 cm taller than in other treatments. In the Beyaz-Altun variety, the same treatment also resulted in taller main stems, reaching 102–107 cm.

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